

Feedback for the AI Governance Framework Checklist

Item from the UKER checklist	s1	s2	s3	s4	s5	s6	s7	s8
1 Subdivision into - AI system for use in clinical care (medical device)/AI system for use in clinical care (medical device) - AI systems for use in research projects Application there has an impact on patient care	yes	yes	yes	Conditionally yes I would categorize AI systems according to risk.	yes		General comment: The checklist does not generally address the issue of data protection and IT security, although these issues play an important role in any use of AI systems.	yes
1.1 Brief description of the planned use case, including the user group affected and any planned integration with other UKER IT applications () (free text)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes		yes
1.1.1 Use in accordance with the intended purpose - I hereby confirm that in the usage scenario described above, the AI system is used exactly as intended by the manufacturer. - The usage scenario described above does not correspond 100% to the intended purpose described by the manufacturer/developer, because ... (please explain below)	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes		yes
1.2 Publication(s)/documentation used to assess the trustworthiness of the AI system (free text)	yes	yes	yes	yes	No, suggest at least distinguishing between research and healthcare contexts	yes		yes
1.3 Autonomy of the AI system (please note Art. 14 EU AI Regulation) - The AI system leads to direct intervention in the care of a patient without a human being being able to verify the system's decision (100% autonomy). - The result of the AI system is always evaluated by a human being, so that it is also possible to modify the result before a corresponding care process for a patient or patient (no autonomy) - In certain situations, the use of the AI system may result in autonomous intervention in the care of a patient (without a human being being able to verify the system's decision) (partial autonomy). In this case, please describe the potential autonomous action and explain why you believe the associated risk to the patient is acceptable.	yes	yes	yes	Conditionally yes There should also be a "no" option for "no contact with patient care."	yes	yes	Conditionally. Yes. According to our understanding of the directive, checking the first checkbox means that the system should not be used. This needs to be noted here, as it no longer makes sense to continue filling out the questionnaire at this point. Similar considerations may apply to the third checkbox, depending on how the directive is interpreted.	Yes, but this list disregards a likely occurrence of automation bias, i.e., habituation when checking the AI system output, so that the initially strict control quickly slackens when the system is performing "well." In this case, manual quality assurance processes may need to be requested by the user (documentation of the check, dual control principle, etc.). Due to the diversity of AI applications, there is a big difference between whether an unsuitable therapy is carried out on the basis of an AI decision, leading to the death of the patient, or whether it is "merely" a matter of measurement deviations. Furthermore, the risk is not a fixed quantity, but depends significantly on the variable probability of occurrence and the expected harm to the patient. The question here should therefore be what measures are taken to minimize the probability of occurrence (and possibly also the damage).
1.4 Risk of discrimination against patient groups I hereby confirm that I have reviewed the available literature/documentation and verified that the use of this AI system does not pose a risk of bias in the AI system's decisions based on the data used to develop the AI system, which could lead to discrimination against individual patient groups.	yes	No I also think this is impossible. I would not be able to guarantee for my clinical AI system in use. What could be done is to ask some kind of confirmations from the company during the procurement. Still then I think companies only can confirm this to the best of their knowledge, probably nobody would guarantee.	hein "that there is no risk in using this AI system.", I do not think that anybody can confirm that in such strong wording. It might be altered to something like (general meaning, obviously the wording can vary). I confirm that based on the literature/documentation in my knowledge, the system does not seem to exhibit any bias/discrimination, etc. with respect to the following biases: list of biases that the developers have tested.	Conditionally yes Difficult To the best of our knowledge, every effort has been made to minimize the risk of bias, and we assure you that the system will be revised if any bias becomes known.	No, I am not familiar with the legal requirements, but I would personally think that a distinction should be made between known and unknown bias. A known bias ("not suitable for use with patient group X") seems unproblematic to me. I am still not familiar with the regulations surrounding products, intended uses, liability issues, etc., but I would assume that in the case of commercial products for healthcare use, the manufacturer is also responsible for testing and liability. An employee or clinic wishing to purchase a product will hardly be able to make a final assessment or take responsibility on the basis of documentation alone.	No—medical devices that may be excluded from use in certain patient groups/consultations should be taken into account. See also the article from Rostock. It also seems difficult to make a final definitive assessment given constant developments (and changes in the patient population). Would periodic monitoring be useful?	No. The guarantee that there is no risk of bias when using an AI system is utopian. In the case of medical devices, this is already checked during the approval process. In a research context, it is not necessary to prove this. At most in this case, it is reasonable to require justification of why the advantages of using an AI system clearly outweigh the risk of bias.	No. In a medical context, it is practically impossible to ensure with absolute certainty that there is no risk, as AI systems are often trained on historical data that may contain inherent biases. These biases can arise from factors such as unequal representation of patient groups (e.g., gender, age, ethnicity) or systemic biases in the underlying data, the training data for purchased third-party developments is almost never directly accessible, making it unrealistic to always be able to detect bias in the data itself. On the other hand, if the bias of the system is known, it can still be used effectively for patient groups that are not discriminated against, provided that the results are always classified correctly. The claim of complete freedom from bias is not only methodologically but also ethically problematic, as it suggests an inappropriate level of certainty. It would be better to tone down the statement, for example: "I have reviewed the available literature/documentation and verified that measures have been taken in the use of this AI system to minimize the risk of bias that could lead to discrimination against individual patient groups. However, continuous review remains necessary to identify and address potential risks at an early stage."
1.5 Verification of the data used for training/developing the AI system - I hereby confirm that I have verified the data used for the training/development of the AI system and its representativeness for the patients to be treated at the UKER on the basis of the available literature/documentation	yes	No again, this is something to ask to the companies	No "their representativeness for the patients to be treated at the UKER" maybe add something like "at the time of the system development" to take into consideration the dataset shift	The same as above. Minimize risk, act to the best of your knowledge and belief	No. See 1.4. I am not familiar with the regulations surrounding products, intended uses, liability issues, etc., in detail, but I would assume that in the case of commercial products for healthcare use, the manufacturer is also responsible for checking and assuming liability. An employee or clinic wishing to purchase a product will hardly be able to assess or take responsibility for this on the basis of documentation. Also with regard to 1.4 and 1.5: It would make sense for institutions to pool their expertise in this area and offer appropriate "AI consulting" or similar services, as well as dedicated environments for monitoring (see below).	No – this assessment appears very subjective. The framework conditions to be taken into account should be described in more detail.	No. The training data is usually not available. Even attempts to use statistical parameters to prove the representativeness of the training data are not possible at this stage.	
2 Planned implementation process (including training for affected users) (please note Art. 13 EU AI Regulation) Please briefly describe the training measures you have planned to train future users of the AI system not only in how to use the system, but also in relation to the specific risks that may be associated with the use of this AI system (free text).	yes	yes Training is essential and should be documented	yes			yes		Yes, but who checks this training plan and what happens in the event of an impractical or unusable training plan? Amendment/addition: It might be useful to provide a framework document or checklist here
3 In the case of an AI system for use in research projects, it has an impact on patient care - A study protocol was drawn up for the planned use of the AI system in a research context, submitted to the Ethics Committee of FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg, and approved by them.	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	See comments on the directive		yes
4 Recording obligations (please note Art. 12 EU AI Regulation) - I am aware of the requirements for the recording obligations of AI systems in accordance with Art. 12 EU AI Regulation. These will be complied with in the AI system to be introduced. We will verify the log files generated by the AI system at regular intervals to ensure the trustworthiness and quality of the AI system throughout its entire life cycle.	yes	yes	yes	yes	No, similar to 1.4 and 1.5. Should manufacturers also be held accountable in the commercial sector? Institutional support and dedicated expertise, etc. are necessary for monitoring.	No - How often must documentation be provided?		Yes, but the duration of the "regular intervals" should be specified/queried here.
5 Other Place, date, and signature of the applicant	yes	yes	yes	yes				yes